

IMPACT OF INDIVIDUAL CULTURAL VALUES ON UNIVERSITY IMAGE: A GENDER BASED COMPARISON IN HIGHER EDUCATION SECTOR OF PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Cultural values and gender play an important role in brand management. The purpose of current research was to find out the influence of individual cultural values on university image. It further explained the role of gender in the relationship between individual cultural values and university image. The quantitative research methodology was adopted to achieve the basic objectives of current research. The questionnaire-based survey conducted to collect the 842 dully filled responses using stratified random sampling technique. The findings of current research showed that collectivism, long term orientation, power distance, and uncertainty avoidance positively influenced university image. However, masculinity did not influence university image. Similarly, gender played a role in the relationships from collectivism, long term orientation, and power distance to university image. Contrary to it, gender played no role in the paths from masculinity and uncertainty avoidance to university image among students. The future studies may include vertical and horizontal collectivism, role of gender, region, age and other demographics. Likewise, other brand equity constructs such as university awareness, university perceived quality, university loyalty may be incorporated to further expand the model in future.

INTRODUCTION

Brand management has been under focus of researchers for the last three decades (Abbas, 2014; Amin & Nika, 2018; Khattak et al., 2015; Veloutsou & Guzman, 2017). Among others, customer based brand equity model has been the most famous and most practiced model of brand management (Heding et al., 2008). Similarly, Aaker's (Aaker, 1991) and Keller's (Keller, 1993) theories brought about novelty in brand management. The most important dimensions of both models have been brand awareness, brand image, perceived brand quality, brand loyalty, and brand resonance (Aaker, 1991;

Keller, 1993). Eventually, brand image construct has been the most famous and the most practiced worldwide (Ali et al., 2021; Coudounaris et al., 2024; Wei, 2024).

Cultural school of thought in brand management helps in building, promoting and sustaining the brand culturally. Cultural school of thought focuses upon the cultural values of branding company rather than the cultural values of customers. It helps in transforming an iconic brands to cultural icons and cultural artifacts (Heding et al., 2020). As per knowledge, previously, the focus has been upon the

cultural values of organizations and country of origin rather than cultural values of customers to build brand associations/image. Brand image refers to a portrait of a brand in customer mind (Sugita & Handayani, 2024). Similarly, brand image stands for a set of associations in customer mind (David, 1996). In the light of cultural school of thought, these associations to be made in corroboration with the cultural values of customers (Salciuviene et al., 2009). Reflecting that cultural values influence brand image. The present research explains cultural values at individual level and their impact on brand (university) image. After the inception of Higher Education Commission of Pakistan (HEC), there have been more than 206 higher education institutions and universities in Pakistan (HEC, 2019; Khan et al., 2021), paving the way for intense competition, pushing universities to adopt modern university branding methods to compete within the country (Hamed et al., 2022). The university associations built through individual cultural values among students make them strong, favorable, and unique which helps a university to compete in the market. None of the previous research has studied this relationship empirically. The current research investigates the influence of individual cultural values on university image in higher education sector of Pakistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The brand management having consumer based school of thought encapsulates information processing theory (IPT) which provides customer based brand equity (Heding et al., 2008). The IPT focuses upon receiving, filtering, storing, retrieving, and using information thus developing a cognitive man, yet having no contextual influence of culture and society (Heding et al., 2008). IPT explains the procedure of consumer choices. A customer mind filters from information composed of multiple choices and selects from them particular information in terms of nodes. Thus, these nodes interconnect and link with one another. Nodes are named brands and links are named associations/images. Moreover, there have been multiple portions in human brain like ventral cortex, mid brain, and information processing streams in which cultural values already residing and ultimately influence the incoming

information (Mohanty, 2021; Park & Huang, 2010). Once the brand and its relative branding effort generate a stimulus, it comes under filtration of customer mind due to cultural values of that customer. It states that cultural values influence the information processing and cognition process of a customer mind. The information processing, cognitive process, and the cultural values occur in the same portion of human brain, filtering incoming information due to already existing cultural values of customer. The information is filtered which does not corroborate with the cultural values of customer. The nodes, the links, and the cultural values all retrieved, while a customer receives a similar stimulus from the environment. Therefore, IPT and cognitive consumer approach provide the foundations of CBBE model. The CBBE model major constructs found to be brand awareness, brand image, brand perceived quality, brand loyalty, brand resonance out of which brand awareness and brand image form brand knowledge (Keller, 1993). Brand knowledge-being the knowledge about brand retrieved in human brain subject to strength, favorability, and uniqueness of associations (links) about the brand (nodes) which ultimately build, develops, and synthesizes a cognition process in consumer mind (Chatzipanagiotou et al., 2019; Heding et al., 2008). The consumer approach of brand management emerges from consumer behavior. Aaker (1991) and Keller (1993) provide two main streams of constructs in consumer approach-CBBE. Aaker (1991) focused on brand equity and Keller (1993) provided the concept of brand knowledge resulting into CBBE pyramid. The knowledge about cultural values of consumer plays pivotal role in the development, launching, sustaining, and marinating a brand (Loo & Hackley, 2013b). It states that knowledge about cultural values of customers is vital to project a brand and build consumer-brand relationship. Henry (1976) argues that cultural values have got a significant impact on consumer behavior. Similarly, the influence of cultural values on brand equity constructs has been studied previously (see, e.g., Chegini et al., 2016; Tarhani & Janfadaei, 2017). Han et al. (2021) empirically found that cultural values positively influence brand equity and its antecedents. Furthermore, their research recommends investigating the same relationships in

varying study settings. Chatzipanagiotou et al. (2019) studies the relationships between cultural values and CBBE across different cultures of Germany and Greece, while using collectivism/individualism (Hofstede, 1983) and found that collectivism positively influences CBBE. Similarly, uncertainty avoidance and power distance impact brand perceptions and consumer choices resulting into brand associations. It was recommended to further study the same constructs of CBBE along individual cultural values of consumers. It shows that there is a lack of comprehensive study on the relationship of individual cultural values and brand image. All the previous works on CBBE has been done conceptually (Keller et al., 2011) and no empirical research conducted on the influence of individual cultural values on brand image (see, e.g., Chatzipanagiotou et al., 2019). Similarly, a few studies have investigated brand management in the higher education sector (see, e.g., Christodoulides, Michaelidou, Cadogan, & Veloutsou, 2015; Farjam and Hongyi, 2016; Taleghani and Almasi, 2011). Ahmad and Dar (2015) claim of very little or no branding in the higher education sector of Pakistan. Logically reasoning, students are not considered customers of university educational services. Moreover, it is common practice not to consider students as customers. Ali and Ahmed (2018b) claim that universities do not build long term relationships with students resulting in little alumni memberships, university endorsements, and university associations. In Pakistan, mere work conducted about collectivism, uncertainty avoidance, and power distance (see, e.g., Kashif, Ramayah, & Sarifuddin, 2016) in relationship to university image, quality, satisfaction, and switching cost (see, e.g., Butt and Rehman, 2010; Isani & Virk, 2005). It shows a research gap in the relationship of all individual cultural values and university image.

Brand

In view of American Marketing Association (AMA), brand refers to the name, logo, symbol, layout, or any other feature which differentiates a branded product from non-branded products or product category. Where, 'any other features' gives way to intangibles like services in definition of brand (Wood, 2000). Similarly, Hakala et al. (2012) say

brand has more features and characteristics instead of simple non branded product in order to consummate same needs and wants of customers.

Brand Image

Reynolds (1965) describes brand image being a picture in customer mind organized and composed of various clues after cognitive selection from various clues available. Kotler (1988) defines brand image as being set of beliefs held in customer mind about the brand. Aaker (1991) defines brand image as a set of associations held in customer mind about brand. Aaker (1992) further said that these set of associations being integrated in certain mode. Biel (1992) defined brand image being the brand name having a set of certain features and associations. Similarly, brand image being the set of associations held in mind of customers (Kim, 2012). Moreover, the psychological and societal factors also influence the development of a mental map or schema in customer minds known as brand image. It states that psychological and social factors also influence in the development of brand image paving the way for influence of cultural values on brand image.

Keller (2004) states marketing efforts build strong, favorable, and unique associations resulting into a brand image. Brand image operationalized through strength, favorability and uniqueness of associations with the brand. It is further claimed that unique associations in terms of tangible or intangible aspects (real or perceived) make the brand purchase decision rational, convenient, and repeat patronage for customers (Brown & Carpenter, 2000). Hsieh, Pan, and Setiono (2004) explain that a strong brand image helps customers in differentiating competing brands to fulfill their needs. Similarly, brand image helps in development of business strategy and marketing efforts of a company in accordance with customer needs and wants (Keller, 1993; Aaker, 1991). A strong brand image builds positive attitude of customers, increased market share of company and ultimately having sustained competitive advantage over other competing (Park, Jaworski, & MacInnis, 1986). Many empirical studies (Aaker, 1991; Biel, 1992; Brown & Carpenter, 2000; Chen, Chen, & Huang, 2012a; Doostar, Asil, & Behrang, 2013; Keller, 1993; Kandampully & Suhartanto, 2000; Koo, 2003) show that a strong, favorable and

unique brand image results in loyalty, equity, and resonance.

Alves and Raposo (2010) operationalized university image as,

“Academic reputation, campus appearance, cost, personal attention, location, distance from home, graduate and professional preparation, career placement, among others” (p. 75).

It can be said that a university’s image is made up of various aspects. The following, inter alia, are the relatively more important aspects: academic standing of the university among other universities, overall infrastructure of the institution, students’ overall expenses throughout the total degree duration, individual attention and focus of the faculty on the students, site of the campus, proximity (distance) of the university to a student’s residence, preparation for academic examinations and for real-life challenges during jobs, career counseling and career management.

Similarly, gender plays an important role in brand management. It is evident from previous studies that brand managers do branding in the form of brand gender. Branding is done in accordance with the consumers’ gender. Branding for a masculine society is done by encapsulating masculine values and traits in the brand. Similarly, branding for a feminine society is done by encapsulating feminine values and traits in the brand. It resolves the issue of brand identity (Lieven & Hildebrand, 2016). In the current research, gender refers to the male and female students of a university. Gender influences customer-based brand equity constructs and their interrelationships. Gender sometimes defines the identity of a brand as either masculine or feminine (Tan et al., 2012; Carvalho et al., 2020).

Culture

Culture defined as “the collective programming of the mind that distinguishes the members of one group or category of people than that of others”. It states the overall understanding of individuals to comprehend in their respective context and upbringing. It further states that culture being a unifying force between individuals and groups that tie them up. Another view about culture represents values, beliefs, norms, and behavioral patterns of a

national group (Leung et al., 2005). Hofstede (2011) further explained culture into its various dimensions/orientations. *First*, collectivism discusses people forming groups or teams joined by family ties—rather far relatives considered impacting the decision of individuals. Moreover, the family protects its members for being loyal with the family. Contrary to it, people are self-centered in an individualistic society and care only for their immediate family members. In individualist cultures, there is an “I” consciousness, a stronger right to privacy, others are considered as individuals as well, adult franchise, professionalism over personal attachment, and the word “I” is used more frequently. Meanwhile, in a collectivist culture, people are born into and connected to large families. There is a “we” consciousness, a focus on belonging, others are considered either as part of the group or not part of the group, votes are based on overall group decisions, and relationships overshadow tasks. *Second*, long-term orientation (LT) versus short-term orientation (ST) describes the attention and focus of individuals on present or future events respectively. Furthermore, LT-success or failure related to future based on effort, whereas ST- success or failure related to past or present based on luck of the individual. *Third*, masculinity-femininity relates to social aspects of a society related to male and female roles. *Fourth*, power distance (PO) relates to the less powerful in a society considering the power being distributed unequally within society. Similarly, certain societies and nations considered more power distant than that of others. *Fifth*, uncertainty avoidance explains the degree to which members of society feel uncertain and uncomfortable with new unknown situations. High uncertainty avoidance countries and cultures feel comfortable with rules, regulations, standard operating procedures, code of conduct, and absolute truth. People of high uncertainty avoidance countries focus on singularity of context and ideology. The operational definitions of university image and individual cultural values given in Table 1 below,

Table 1

Operational definitions of brand image and culture

Constructs	Operational Definitions	References
Brand Image	Brand image refers to an overall picture or a set of associations created in the minds of students about a university in terms of the favorability of associations, strength of associations, and uniqueness of associations.	(Keller, 1993), (Bravo et al., 2009), (Hong & Lee, 2012).
Culture	Culture refers to the individual cultural values of power distance, masculinity, uncertainty avoidance, long-term orientation, and collectivism of university students.	(Mooij & Hofstede, 2010; Nazim & Wajidi, 2016; Méndez et al., 2009a; Yoo et al., 2011)

Framework

It is considered very important and quite practical for a firm to address cultural values of customers while creating brand image (Raza & Zaman, 2021). Similarly, developing brand image in accordance with cultural orientation of country makes a brand to be successful and increases profit of a company (Krueger & Nandan, 2008). Personal cultural values impact brand image (Salciuviene et al., 2009b). It states that strong, favorable, and unique set of associations in accordance with cultural orientations of customers develop a strong brand image on them. Collectivism addresses group thinking, collective decision making and admiration for adherence to family, parents, teachers and institutional norms (Hofstede, 1983; Nazim & Wajidi, 2016). Cultural values index show that Pakistan has a score of 86 representing Pakistan to be a highly collectivist society (Insights, 2019). Collectivist society develops respecting teachers, little discussion with teacher representing honor for teacher, conformity to teachers' thoughts and university customs being admired, whereas, going against university norms and rules, differing with teachers and classmates considered contrary to group thinking and ultimately collectivism (Dennehy, 2015; Mitsis, 2004; Yoo et al., 2011b).

Previous study in conducted in Pakistan shows that collectivism influences brand loyalty (Kazmi et al., 2020). Kazmi et al. (2020) suggest to find the influence of individual cultural values power distance, uncertainty avoidance, time orientation, masculinity/femininity CBBE various constructs such as brand awareness, brand image, brand perceived quality, and brand loyalty. Similarly, Li (2021) conducts a study about influence of

uncertainty on CBBE, suggests to further study the influence of power distance, collectivism, masculinity/femininity, and uncertainty avoidance on different constructs of CBBE. Adherence and compliance with group thinking of others (collectivism) about the symbolic (impression and reputation) and functional (services) image of university build student's positive experience based associations (experiential image) (Ali et al., 2021a) with university. Collectivism based associations in students mind develop strong, favorable, and unique university image which differentiates than other universities. As per knowledge of researcher, such a relationship has still not been explained in any of previous research. Therefore, it is thought that collectivism impacts university image. From the above discussion, one can hypothesize that,

Hypothesis 1: Collectivism positively and significantly influences university image.

A set of strong, favorable, and unique associations form brand image in customer mind. The more strong, favorable, an unique these associations are, the better the brand image in customer mind (Ali et al., 2021a; Heding et al., 2008, 2020). These associations built in subconscious part of human mind, so the more stronger they are, the more conveniently these can be recalled from memory (Park & Huang, 2010). Humans use cognitive process for selection and filtration of stimuli from their surroundings. For this cognitive process initiation and completion, sensory organs being used (Hassana et al., 2021; Richter & Hütter, 2021; Zhang, 2021). In this vain, individual cultural values residing in sub conscious part of human brain plays

deciding factor about filtration of various stimuli (Wang & Wang, 2021; Wang, 2021). Cultural values influence brand image (Han et al., 2021a). Roth (1995) stated that LT influences corporate brand image. LT reflects individuals of a society focusing on long term objectives and goals in their life, and in ST individuals in a society focus on short term objectives and goals in their life (Hofstede, 1983). The society of Pakistan has a score of 50 on cultural values scale (Insights, 2019) representing that people of Pakistan have been partially long term oriented and partially short term oriented. Whereas, students in a university have been found to be long term oriented (Abubakar & Mokhtar, 2015). Because, logically, students come to university to complete their degree programs to fulfill their long-term objectives to be successful and get settled in their lives. The universities focusing on the students learning financial management, persistence in education, being studious, long term career management, and hard work results in success in future (Dennehy, 2015; Yoo et al., 2011b) form university image. Previous researches in Pakistan conducted on relationship of social responsibility, service quality, satisfaction, and trust with student loyalty in universities (Latif et al., 2021), university reputation influence on student satisfaction, brand image influences brand equity (Alam, 2016), influence of perceived university image on student loyalty (Ali & Ahmed, 2018b), the academic and nonacademic services influence student loyalty (Khan et al., 2020). As per researcher knowledge, no previous study discussed the influence of long-term orientation on university image. From the above discussion, one can hypothesize that:

Hypothesis 2: Long term orientation positively and significantly influences university image.

The score of Pakistan on masculinity scale found to be 50 (Insights, 2019). Previous study shows that individual cultural values influence CBBE constructs (Han et al., 2021a). Similarly, masculinity is composed of assertiveness, money and personal success (Bowman & Filar, 2017). Students being admired, encouraged, and competition valued in masculine societies (Dennehy, 2015). Masculine societies focus upon professionalism, logical analysis, active and forcible approach, and gender based jobs

and roles in a society for which males considered more suitable than females (Dennehy, 2015) forming customer associations in terms of university image (Heathy, 2020; Iskhakova et al., 2020). Students in masculine cultures (Park & Huang, 2010) expect good university ranking ensuring better career, handsome earning, social recognition and admiration, and success in competitive environment after graduation create (Dennehy, 2015; Hofstede et al., 2010; Yoo, 2009; Yoo et al., 2011b) a stronger, favorable and unique set of associations in students' minds about a university (Keller et al., 2011). Previous study (Soomro, 2019) discussed individual level collectivist values impacting perceived quality and loyalty, collectivism influencing brand meaning (Sarki et al., 2012), cultural values impacting CBBE constructs (Shah et al., 2020), while having paucity of research on masculinity influencing university image in Pakistan. From the above discussion, one can hypothesize that,

Hypothesis 3: Masculinity positively and significantly influences university image.

The score of Pakistan found to be 55 on power distance scale (Insights, 2019) showing that less powerful individuals in the society accept that inequalities in society exist. Brand image has dimensions of favorability of associations, the strength of associations, and uniqueness of associations (Aaker, 1996a; Keller et al., 2011). Brand image is created in the form of nodes in the brain. Each node represents a particular brand, and the links or associations between these nodes represent brand image (Keller et al., 2011). Brand knowledge (Keller, 2001) (brand awareness and brand image) develops the cognitive understanding in the consumer's mind, and its retrieval depends on the strength, favorability and uniqueness of these associations (links) of the brand (node) (Heding et al., 2008; Park & Huang, 2010). Societies in which there exists a certain high level of power distance, there also exists a strong distinction factor in the mind of a student about the high ranking university and low ranking university (brand) (Dennehy, 2015; Mitsis, 2004; Yoo et al., 2011b) which turns into university image due to experience (Bernarto et al., 2020) of studying there. Moreover, in high power distance countries, university image (reputation) is

key ingredient university equity (Iskhakova et al., 2020). Iskhakova et al. (2020) have focused only upon university reputation which is symbolic dimension of brand, however, left other functional and experiential (Bernarto et al., 2020) dimensions like good impression, commitment, and consistency, friendly and warm image among students. Ultimately, the high power distance aspects like consulting with family seniors, elders, asking the opinion of seniors, parents, social interaction with teachers and alumni, agreeableness with the decisions of parents, teachers and elders, are such patterns in the subconscious of student that make up the strong, favorable and unique set of associations based university reputation, experience and attachment in student mind, university commitment towards students, university contribution to society, student giving respect to teachers, keeps them loyal (Bernarto et al., 2020) with their university. Previous studies conducted in Pakistan focused upon influence of power distance on student performance (Khalid & Iraqi, 2020), corporate and brand image, trust, perceived value, satisfaction and service quality and resulting into retention, commitment, recommendation and positive word of mouth (Tariq et al., 2020), power distance theoretically related to image (Iskhakova et al., 2020) but still not empirically tested and supported in Pakistan. Moreover, up to researcher knowledge there is paucity of comprehensive study about the relationship of power distance with university image in Pakistan. In high power distance countries customers show low impulse buying behavior and show high customer loyalty and vice versa (Wang & Lalwani, 2019). Therefore, it is thought that power distance impacts university image. From the above discussion, one can hypothesize that:

Hypothesis 4: Power distance positively and significantly impacts Brand (university) image.

The score of Pakistan found to be 70 on uncertainty avoidance scale (Insights, 2019). Uncertainty

avoidance describes the tendency to avoid the risk and uncertain situations (Hofstede et al., 2010; Nazim & Wajidi, 2016). Similarly, brand image refers to a set of associations attached with the brand (Keller, 2001). Brand image (associations) is measured in terms of a favorable, strong and unique set of associations (Keller et al., 2011). Students have varying associations/image subject to differing cultural values. Uncertainty avoiding orientation of customers not only keep them away from unknown and inexperienced brands but also tends them toward building associations and attachment with experienced brand (Roth, 1995). Usually the associations/image about university built through teacher instructions to students in classroom, teaching being 'guru' induce career goals among students (Hofstede et al., 2010), explaining requirements for academic success, defining university rules, explaining university rules and instructions compliance benefits, and rewards to students for either complying or not complying with university procedures (Dennehy, 2015; Hofstede et al., 2010; Yoo et al., 2011a). Students not conforming to teacher instructions and university rules considered disloyalty (Hofstede et al., 2010). Previously, Klongthong et al. (2020) findings support the direct and positive relationship of uncertainty avoidance with corporate brand image. Raza and Zaman (2021b) studied luxury brands purchase intention based on cultural values and they recommend to further study the association of cultural beliefs with brand image. Moreover, Shah et al. (2020) found that cultural values impact CBBE in Pakistan. As per researcher knowledge no previous research has focused on the relationship of uncertainty avoidance and university image. Therefore, one can hypothesize that:

Hypothesis 5: Uncertainty avoidance positively and significantly influences brand image.

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework: Individual Cultural Values Impact Brand Image

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The current research uses quantitative research methodology in which the deduction research approach adopted to infer the results. Similarly, the present research uses quantitative methods, which consists of several steps explained ahead (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010, 2019). The chosen research strategy is the survey (Lakshmi, 2020). With the help of survey, a large number of students from universities accessed, and their responses can be generated for better results generalization of current research (Sekaran & Bougie, 2019). The data have been collected through a questionnaire-based survey (Cheema et al., 2021; Iskhakova et al., 2017; Khan et al., 2021; Latif et al., 2021; Li, 2021a) to answer the fundamental research objective, which is to understand the influence of individual cultural values on university image. The scale for brand (university) image was adapted from Keller (1993), Bravo et al. (2009), and Hong and Lee (2012). The individual cultural values scale adopted from Yoo et al. (2011). These scales have been previously used in academic research by many authors (see, e.g., Aaker, 1996a, 1996b; Buil et al., 2008; Jamal & Anastasiadou, 2009; Keller, 1993; Pappu et al., 2005; Pinar et al., 2014; Yoo et al., 2011b; Yoo & Shin, 2017). Cronbach's alpha (CA) and composite reliability (CR) test are applied for checking the scale

reliability (Hair Jr et al., 2021; Purwanto & Sudargini, 2021; Rughoobur-Seetah et al., 2021).

The higher education sector of Pakistan has been flourishing, particularly since 2000, courtesy of meticulous efforts of the federal government through budget enhancement, policy-making, etc., in collaboration with HEC (Ahmad, 2013; Khan et al., 2021). HEC has done a commendable job in bringing the quality of higher education in the country at international quality standards (Khan et al., 2021). It has resulted in the development of the perceptions of students regarding comparing universities, ultimately serving as a stimulus for HEIs to come up with marketing/branding strategies to attract national and international students. However, little research is conducted in Pakistan to comprehend the concept of brand management among universities (Alam et al., 2020; Khattak et al., 2015; Shah et al., 2020). The student population under consideration for the present research represents all universities and higher education degree-awarding institutions of Pakistan, since, students pool can provide invaluable standard to calculate generalizability across cultures (Gächter, 2010). The major reason for population selection of university students was because universities have heterogeneous students' from all around the country belonging to different cultures, and capital city like Islamabad has people from different parts of

Pakistani society as well, bringing their cultural values with them into Islamabad, thus fulfills the requirements of the abovementioned research objectives and their respective estimates criteria (Hakala et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2014). The sampling unit of the study was individuals (students) enrolled in graduation and post-graduation degree programs of universities under the administration of the Government of Pakistan.

The research utilizes a stratified random sampling approach because individuals (students) coming from different cultural orientations and provinces may have equal chance of occurrence as being true representative sample showing characteristics of overall target population under consideration (Levin, 2011; Saunders & Lewis, 2017). The sample size should be $382.5 \approx 383$ per Krejcie and Morgan (1970). Zikmund’s sample size estimation formula and Saunders table of approximate sample size for a population of 1,000,000 and above at a 5% margin of error also support the sample size of 384 (Islam et al., 2021; Saunders & Lewis, 2017; Saunders, 2011b; Zikmund et al., 2013). Similarly, students in a university belong to almost all regions of a country and represent their cultural values (Park & Rabolt, 2009). Consequently, the sample has been taken from the federally chartered universities in Islamabad, which is reflective of the cultural values of all students in Pakistan (Jegade, 2020). Moreover, five out of 10 top-ranking universities in Pakistan are in Islamabad per HEC’s list (HEC, 2019). Hence, it can be inferred that the five top brands (universities) are in Islamabad, which fulfills the sample

requirement to study the branding of universities in Pakistan, to represent total number of students in higher education institutions of Pakistan (Jegade, 2020).

The Partial Least Square - Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) used in investigating the research hypotheses along examining reliability and validity through Cronbach’s alpha, composite reliability, average variance extracted, model fit, confirmatory factor analysis using (cross loadings, and outer loading) for measurement model and bootstrapping technique to test the significance of paths for structural model in order to generalize the results to the target population (Ghauri et al., 2020; Hays & McKibben, 2021; Lakshmi, 2020; Lo et al., 2020).

RESULTS

Out of 1001, as many as 936 respondents’ duly filled questionnaires were collected, out of which 842 questionnaires were correctly and duly filled. The survey elicited an 84.11% response rate, which by any standard is a good response rate showing very little response bias. The male respondents had been 512 (60.8 %), and female respondents have been 330 (39.2 %). The estimated results of ICVSCALE used in current research found to be as CO=61.99, LT=76.86, MA=79.39, PO=54.09, and UN=77.71. There has been almost similarity in results of current research and Hofstede results (Insights, 2019) except LT found 76.86 and 19, and MA found 63.51 and 50, in current research and Hofstede respectively.

Table 2
Comparison of ICVSCALE and Geert Hofstede Results

Sr. No.	Scale	Results	Geert Hofstede Results (Insights, 2019)
1	CO	61.99	95
2	LT	76.86	19
3	MA	79.39	50
4	PO	54.09	55
5	UN	77.71	70

Measurement model

Reliability

The minimum acceptable value for both Cronbach’s alpha and composite reliability is 0.70 (Suriyenty et al., 2014). Table 3 shows the Cronbach’s alpha

values for the female and male data sets and the composite reliability values of the constructs of BI, CO, LT, MA, PO, and UN. All values exceed the minimum acceptable value of 0.7 (Khoshtaria et al., 2020; Lodhi et al., 2014; Santos, 1999), thus

indicating that all constructs are reliable considering the both-genders, female, and male data sets.

Table 3
Reliability Statistics

Constructs	Both Genders		Female		Male	
	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
BI	0.833	0.889	0.860	0.899	0.827	0.886
CO	0.753	0.858	0.755	0.860	0.777	0.856
LT	0.713	0.839	0.741	0.847	0.694	0.830
MA	0.787	0.862	0.754	0.848	0.784	0.857
POD	0.821	0.873	0.859	0.886	0.805	0.867
UN	0.839	0.886	0.847	0.897	0.833	0.882

Convergent Validity

The convergent validity is measured through average variance extracted. The threshold value of acceptance of AVE should be 0.5 (Khoshtaria et al., 2020; Lodhi

et al., 2014; Santos, 1999). Therefore, the Table 4 shows that all the values of AVE greater than 0.6 showing convergent validity.

Table 4
Average Variance Extracted

Constructs	Both Genders AVE	Females AVE	Males AVE
BI	0.668	0.641	0.661
CO	0.669	0.672	0.600
LT	0.635	0.650	0.621
MA	0.610	0.653	0.601
POD	0.634	0.608	0.621
UN	0.609	0.684	0.599

Model Fit

The NFI values for the both-genders, female, and male data sets is close to 1, and all values fall within the range of 0.703 to 0.806, indicating good model fit. The value of SRMR should be less than 0.08 (Hu & Bentler, 1999). In the present study, the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) values obtained are 0.054 (both genders), 0.065

(females), and 0.057 (males), values confirming the goodness of fit for all data sets (Hair Jr et al., 2021).

Comparison of R-Square in all data sets

Moreover, Table 5 shows that the BA values (for the both-genders, female and male data sets) show minimum% change from R-square to adjusted R-square (-1.81%, -4.26%, and -3.90%, respectively).

Table 5
Adjusted R-Square Comparison in All Three Data Sets

	Both Genders			Female			Male		
	R ²	R ² Adjusted	% Change	R ²	R ² Adjusted	% Change	R ²	R ² Adjusted	% Change
BI	0.208	0.204	-1.96%	0.219	0.207	-5.79%	0.207	0.199	-4.02%

Structural model

Table 6 shows that Collectivism ($\beta_b=0.170$, $T_b\text{-value}=4.016$, $P_b\text{-value}=0.000$ for both genders) ($\beta_f=0.246$, $T_f\text{-value}=4.064$, $P_f\text{-value}=0.000$ for females), ($\beta_m=0.117$, $T_f\text{-value}=1.987$, $P_f\text{-value}=0.047$ for males) has a significant positive impact on brand image for all three data sets. Long-term orientation ($\beta_b=0.257$, $T_b\text{-value}=5.962$, $P_b\text{-value}=0.000$ for both genders), ($\beta_f=0.194$, $T_f\text{-value}=3.136$, $P_f\text{-value}=0.002$ for females), ($\beta_m=0.342$, $T_f\text{-value}=5.827$, $P_f\text{-value}=0.000$ for males) has a significant positive impact on brand image for all three datasets.

Table 6 further shows a gender-based difference in the impact of long-term orientation on brand (university) image. The LT-BI path is insignificant in the case of females ($\beta=0.113$, $t\text{-value}= 1.823$, $p\text{-value}=0.069$) and significant in the case of males ($\beta=0.201$, $t\text{-value}= 3.365$, $p\text{-value}= 0.009$). The differences between female and male results reflect that males represent long term orientation values than females in relation to brand (university) image. Long-term orientation plays a substantial role by impacting brand (university) image of male students. Long-term orientation plays no role in influencing brand (university) image among female students.

Masculinity ($\beta_b=-0.063$, $T_b\text{-value}=1.764$, $P_b\text{-value}=0.078$ for both genders), ($\beta_f=-0.030$, $T_f\text{-value}=0.503$, $P_f\text{-value}=0.615$ for females), ($\beta_m=-0.040$, $T_m\text{-value}=0.827$, $P_m\text{-value}=0.409$ for males) has no significant impact on brand (university) image for both genders, females, or males. No moderation was

indicated for any of the datasets, as there is no significant impact of masculinity on brand image ($T\text{-value} >1.96$; $P\text{-value} <0.005$) for genders, females, and males.

Table 6 further shows that Power distance ($\beta_b=0.162$, $T_b\text{-value}=4.629$, $P_b\text{-value}=0.000$ for both genders), ($\beta_f=0.118$, $T_f\text{-value}=1.919$, $P_f\text{-value}=0.056$ for females), ($\beta_m=0.182$, $T_m\text{-value}=4.213$, $P_m\text{-value}=0.000$ for males) has a significant positive impact on brand image in cases of both genders and males; the impact was insignificant in the case of females ($T\text{-value} >1.96$; $P\text{-value} < 0.005$).

Uncertainty avoidance ($\beta_b=0.218$, $T_b\text{-value}=5.152$, $P_b\text{-value}=0.000$ for both genders) ($\beta_f=0.204$, $T_f\text{-value}=2.922$, $P_f\text{-value}=0.004$ for females), ($\beta_m=0.197$, $T_m\text{-value}=3.755$, $P_m\text{-value}=0.000$ for males) has a significant positive impact on brand image for all three data sets ($T\text{-values} >1.96$; $P\text{-values} < 0.005$).

Table 6 also shows a gender-based difference in the impact of power distance on brand (university) image. The PO-UI path is insignificant in the case of females ($\beta=0.118$, $t\text{-value}= 1.919$, $p\text{-value}= 0.056$) and significant in the case of males ($\beta=0.182$, $t\text{-value}= 4.213$, $p\text{-value}= 0.000$). The differences between female and male results reflect that males reveal power distance values differently than females in relation to brand (university) image. Power distance plays a substantial role by impacting brand (university) image of male students. It plays no role in influencing brand (university) image among female students.

Table 6
Model Run and Bootstrapping Results

Sr	Paths	Both Genders			Females			Males		
		β	P	Results	β	P	Results	β	P	Results
1	CO -> BI	0.17	<.001	Supported	0.25	<.001	Supported	0.12	0.04	Supported
2	LT -> BI	0.16	<.001	Supported	0.11	0.07	Not-supported	0.20	<.01	Supported
3	MA -> BI	-0.06	0.08	Not-supported	-0.03	0.62	Not-supported	0.04	0.41	Not-supported
4	PO -> BI	0.16	0.000	Supported	0.12	0.056	Not-supported	0.18	<.001	Supported
5	UN -> BI	0.29	0.000	Supported	0.20	0.004	Supported	0.19	<.001	Supported

DISCUSSION

Collectivism impacts brand image positively and significantly. Since the society of Pakistan being collectivist in nature having score of 95 (e.g., see Insights, 2019 and Jamal, 2020), as the result of current research found to be 61.99 being high collectivist students, it has proven to be a detrimental factor in development of brand image. Since collectivists develop a web of associations and bond in their mind about group thinking, it helps in building strong, favorable and unique associations in their mind about the brand. The research reveals that university students during their studies develop strong, unique and favorable university perception/associations in their mind in adherence to their teachers, peers, class fellows and others. The more collective thought process, group thinking, teamwork, congruence with assigned tasks incorporated in university processes of lectures, seminars, assignments, administration, and exams, the better the university image in students' minds. So, a collectivist society has a stronger university image. Parallel to the findings of current research, the previous work of Krautz (2017) establishes that collective brand perceptions influence brand choices in collectivist cultures. Similarly, gender plays a significant role these paths. The path from collectivism to university image found very stronger among females as compared to males i.e almost twice strong. The reason for this as females being more collectivist than males (Dabiriyani Tehrani & Yamini, 2022). Females adhere more to developing collectivist approach about the university image (attributes, functions, ideas, feelings and ranking) (Lee et al., 2014) as compared to their male counterparts. Since females have learned throughout their life to comply with group norms and being subjugated in collectivist cultures (Zeffane, 2020). Moreover, female students more collectively perceive about university image as compared to males. The reason females group adherence is more as compared to males (Arora et al., 2011). Therefore, universities incorporating collectivism in building their image among students appeal more to female students than male students. Similarly, the results of current research about Collectivism found to be almost in coherence with results previous cultural values research

Long term orientation positively and significantly impacts university image. It shows that university image composed of long-term objectives of students appeal to them. The university student's associations toward university are shaped by long term values like achievement, success in future, thrift, and perseverance. If these values incorporated in building university image, then students represent a set of strong, favorable and unique long-term associations with the university. Even, the overall score of Pakistan on LT scale found to be 19, showing that people in society of Pakistan found to be short term oriented-focusing upon past precedence and adherence to traditions (Mujtaba & Habib, 2011). Although previous studies show that whole society of Pakistan have been short term oriented as LT found to be 19 (Insights, 2019), whereas, current research shows the result of LT found to be 76.86 which shows that students in Pakistan found to be having high score on long term orientation. Logically, students in Pakistan focus upon efforts in modern education and thrift, being contrary to normative and traditional society at large in Pakistan. The results also show that students' LT-cultural orientation can be different from the society at large in Pakistan. It is the first study which found the difference between the two genders male and female with respect to LT. The study shows that male found to be long term oriented, whereas females found to be short term oriented. Similarly, gender plays an important role in the path from LT to UI. The path LT-UI found significant in case of male students and found insignificant in case of female students. Male students show long term oriented cultural values. Male students found to be focused on long term orientation, long term planning, achievement, perseverance, thrift, persistence, and success in future values. The university associations built upon these long-term oriented values found to form good reputation, good impression on students, a commitment towards education, and a consistent contribution to society especially among male students. Since, female students are relatively short term oriented to achieve near goals and having lack of long time frame as compared to men (Greene & DeBacker, 2004), so the path from LT to UI in case of female students found insignificant.

Masculinity found to be insignificant in all three paths from MA-UI among genders, females, and males. Masculinity found to be 79.39 in current research, representing highly masculine students in universities of Pakistan. Whereas, Pakistan has score of 50 on masculinity (e.g., see Insights (2019) and Khan et al. (2021), which shows that neither the society is masculine nor feminine rather neutral. The reason being universities do not brand themselves as having gender. Students have been focusing on achievement and success as being masculine, but university is not building associations based on masculinity or femininity rather than being neutral. This neutral value structure of Pakistan society reflected in the path MA-UI. Females attach themselves with both feminine and the masculine brand and males attach themselves with masculine brand, whereas, male does not attach with feminine brand (Neale et al., 2016). The insignificance of masculinity on university image because students found neutral in masculinity-femininity value. Furthermore, neither the university brand gender identity (Hirschman, 2016) has been made by universities nor this concept has been studied in Pakistan so far. Reason being the masculine or feminine brand elicit more favorable brand associations/image more than gender-neutral brands (Lieven et al., 2014).

Power distance positively and significantly impacts university image. The higher power distance orientation helps in building strong, favorable, and unique university associations/image as compared to lower power distance values. Pakistan has an overall score of 55 making it slightly high power distance country (Insights, 2019), and the current research also shows the students of universities in Pakistan found to be high power distance with a score of 54.09. The university associations are influenced by higher power distance cultural value. It states that university should keep herself at a higher power distance position from students to build strong, favorable and unique set of university associations/image in students' minds. Higher power distance elicits good reputation, impression, commitment, and contribution of university towards students. Moreover, it is revealed universities image formed which represent higher power distance than that of other low power distance universities as such

universities show the status and social position of students (Jansson, 2013). Gender also plays an important role in PO-UI path. The path PO-UI found significant among males and insignificant among females. Due to patriarchal society of Pakistan, females don't associate themselves with high power distance, so the path found insignificant among females. A previous study also show that females found neutral on power distance scale (Qureshi & Raja, 2013) in Pakistan, thereby, possibly not affecting university image. Whereas males associate themselves with high power distance, so path found significant. University image/associations built through university reputation, commitment, contribution to society~ makes the university image high power distance among male students, which further corroborate with their gender identity.

Since, the current research shows that students having score of 77.71 and Pakistan scores 70 on uncertainty avoidance scale (Insights, 2019) which shows that the society of Pakistan in general and students of universities in particular highly avoid uncertain situations. The path UA-UI found positive and significant in all three data sets both genders, females and males. Moreover, it was found that the pat UA-UI had no major difference based on gender. Both females and males avoid uncertainty in Pakistan. This cultural value UA illustrated in university associations/ image make such construal in students' mind which turns into strong favorable and unique associations. Well spelled out instructions system, standard operating procedures, rules and regulations, predefined operations of universities make strong, favorable and unique associations in student mind which differentiates a university from other universities. Uncertainty avoidance has become precursor of university image because the students become familiar with the university during their studies due to university reputation, commitment to education, contribution to society and friendly and warm faculty and staff making university associations strong, favorable and unique. Therefore, instead of being in uncertainty, students focus upon more familiar universities.

Overall, uncertainty avoidance has proven to be the strongest predictor of university image. Collectivism has proven to be the strongest predictor of university image among females. Contrary to it, collectivism has

proven to be the weakest predictor of university image among males.

None of the previous research works on individual cultural values and brand image constructs has provided in-depth gender-based comparisons. It is the first study of its nature conducted on the role of gender between individual cultural values and university image. Hence, the present study empirically explained the role of gender in various relationships in the validated model. The comparison between female and male respondents revealed different results in certain relationships, thus notifying policymakers that building university image should be implemented in relation to individual cultural values, and they should be implemented differently for females and males.

Implications

Theoretical implications

The current research supports Aaker's and Keller's brand equity theories. Building, developing, and sustaining brand image in accordance with cultural values of students support synthesis of cultural approach and consumer-based approach. It is the first study which theoretically and empirically joined, tested and justified two schools of thought namely cultural school of thought and consumer-based school of thought of brand management. The current research provided the latest knowledge about scores of various cultural orientations in Pakistan which helps for further research. Previously culture has only been considered as a moderator in various relationships of brand equity and its various constructs, while current research theoretically and empirically supported the direct influence of culture on brand image. Moreover, it is evident from current research that building brand image based upon individual cultural values should be different for males and females. The impact of individual cultural values on brand image is gender specific. Both males and females act differently in these relationships, thus, supporting gender-based theorists' argument of gender specific branding. The findings of current research found to be supporting Geert Hofstede cultural values theory in CO, PO, UN, and not supporting in cultural values LT and MA. Theoretical implication arises about the validity of

Geert Hofstede cultural values theory generalization at individuals' level.

Practical implications

The current research provides individual cultural values-based brand image model for practitioners and brand managers in universities. Building brand image based upon cultural values of consumers increases the chances of success of a brand in the markets. Similarly, university should opt and build current model to better cope with the requirements of building university image. Universities creating their image among students based upon cultural values of students like collectivism, long term orientation, power distance, and uncertainty avoidance perform better than others. Likewise, gender specific university image based upon cultural values of students also help in good branding. Collectivism and uncertainty avoidance help in developing better university image, whereas long term orientation, masculinity, and power distance does not help in building university image among female students. In this regard, universities build university image among females based on collectivism and uncertainty avoidance only. Furthermore, collectivism, long term orientation, power distance, and uncertainty avoidance help in developing university image, whereas, masculinity, does not help in building university image among male students. The managers and practitioners should consider this gender specific university image in accordance with cultural values of university students.

Limitations and future studies

The study has been limited to individual cultural values and university image. The research is limited only to the role of gender from ICV to UI. Cross sectional data collected, and the model validated from students sample in the higher education sector only.

In future the further in-depth usage of vertical and horizontal collectivism, role of gender, region, age and other demographics can be included in future study. Other brand equity constructs like university awareness, university perceived quality, university loyalty etc. can be incorporated to further expand the model. The same model can be tested in other

primary and secondary education sectors and in other countries.

Conclusion

It is concluded that power distance, uncertainty avoidance, long term orientation, and collectivism impact university image. It also reveals that masculinity does not affect university image. It states that university image be built on associations which describe values like Power distance, uncertainty avoidance, long term orientation, and collectivism. Moreover, gender plays an important role in the case of paths from CO-BI, LT-BI, and PO-BI. Gender does not play any role in paths from MA-BI and UN-BI. It states that gender-based university image be built on associations which describe values like collectivism, long term orientation and power distance separately for female and male students in universities.

The study is the first in its nature and scope to find the influence of individual cultural values on university image especially with reference to the role of gender. Finally, none of the previous research has explained these intricate relationships between individual cultural values and brand (university) image in the higher education sector.

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